

Corpus linguistics and AI: #LancsBox X in the context of emerging technologies

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This position paper explores how corpus linguistics can respond to advancements in AI technologies, including large language models (LLMs). Drawing on theoretical debates about meaning creation, it examines two models of human-computer interaction, namely Turing's imitation game, which suggests functional equivalence between successful computer and human communication, and Searle's Chinese room argument, which critiques the idea of genuine understanding by machines. These discussions emphasize the distinction between form and meaning, with meaning grounded in social context and human interaction. The paper then introduces #LancsBox X, a free software tool developed as a response to the challenges of emerging technologies. Designed for efficiency and user experience, #LancsBox X provides advanced functionalities for corpus analysis, including concordancing, collocation analysis and visualization, keyword identification and web scraping. By emphasizing context in language use, the tool demonstrates how computational methods can support linguistic research while addressing the evolving demands of big data analysis.

Keywords: AI; Corpus Linguistics; LLMs; #LancsBox; Technology

1. Introduction

This paper offers a discussion of AI technologies and a possible response of corpus linguistics to these developments. It is based on the theoretical understanding of the field of corpus linguistics in the context of (social) science, fully developed in McEnery and Brezina (2022), which proposes a critical rationalist approach, grounded in functional understanding of language. The discussion of corpus linguistics and AI is particularly timely given the current and future impact of the emerging technologies, the large language models (LLMs) and AI, on our working practices, research and everyday life. It also presents a speculative viewpoint on meaning creation through new technologies, aligning corpus linguistics response with critical evaluations of these technologies in other disciplines such as philosophy (e.g., Peters et al., 2024) and computer science (e.g., Shumailov et al., 2024).

First, let us consider the understanding of the world that we can gain through leveraging the power of AI and LLMs. For instance, we can look at the

“understanding” of the discipline of corpus linguistics itself—note that the word “understanding” is deliberately in quotes here. Figure 1 displays two outputs from two AI tools: ChatGPT, which many readers are familiar with through their various experiments in everyday practice, and Crayon, which synthesizes large amounts of visual data. The definition and visualization of “corpus linguistics” by these tools, can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1.

AI-Generated “Understanding” of Corpus Linguistics (ChatGPT and Crayon)

As can be seen, ChatGPT defines corpus linguistics as

a field of linguistics that involves the collection, analysis, and study of large structured sets of text known as corpora. These corpora can consist of written or spoken language, and they serve as empirical sources for linguistic research. Corpus linguists use these corpora to investigate patterns in language use, such as frequencies, collocations, grammar, and discourse structures. By analyzing extensive collections of text, corpus linguists can gain insights into language variation usage and the way language reflects the cultural and social context in which it is used. Corpus Linguistics is widely used in research, language teaching, and natural language processing applications.

This is a fairly comprehensive definition of corpus linguistics, and although there are a few points that might invite disagreement, overall, the AI tool performed well when defining the field. This represents a stark contrast to the output of the creative AI tool Crayon, which was used to visualize “corpus linguistics”—an image resembling a brain combined with a part of a human

face and neck, which clearly is not directly connected with the abstract notion of corpus linguistics as a discipline or specific examples of its analytical practice. We thus do not know why corpus linguistics should be depicted, even metaphorically, like the image in Figure 1.

Importantly, both of these systems remain opaque, making it challenging to comprehend the process that led to the results presented in Figure 1. The illustration offers a small insight into where we stand today regarding AI technology and LLMs used for data synthesis. The key notion here is "synthesis of large data," a strength of computational technology in consolidating diverse information sources, as evident in the comprehensive definition of corpus linguistics and to a much lesser degree in the image that was created synthetically to visualize "corpus linguistics".

So, how do we make sense of AI outputs? The following paragraphs show two possible theoretical perspectives on computer systems in relation to the key semiotic question of meaning creation. Let us start in the 1950s, which marked the rise of early computational technology. Alan Turing (1950), a renowned thinker in the area of early computer science, discussed the question of whether machines can interact in a human-like manner, framing it as the "imitation game." In this game, three participants are involved: Participant A, a male participant; participant B, a female participant; and participant C, an interrogator or judge. A may provide deceptive answers, while B offers truthful responses, making it challenging for the interrogator (C) to determine who is male and who is female because participant A can lie about his gender identity. Turing proposed that if this game were played with a human and a computer as participants A and B respectively, we can re-define the question of "can machines think?" as the parameters of human-computer interaction within this imitation game. Turing (1950, p. 433) writes:

We now ask the question, "What will happen when a machine takes the part of A in this [imitation] game?" Will the interrogator decide wrongly as often when the game is played like this as he does when the game is played between a man and a woman? These questions replace our original, "Can machines think?"

Turing thus pondered whether the interrogator could distinguish between human and computer responses and if not what the implications would be. This enquiry led to an influential position regarding computer-human interaction held by computer scientists and proponents of the AI technology—when an interrogator cannot distinguish between human and computer responses there may not be a practical difference between how humans and computers operate. Applying this concept to the present, it can be argued, in line with Turing, that, for example, chatbots can successfully replace humans in certain

tasks, if the user cannot tell the difference between a human and a computer answering the question.

In contrast, in a contribution to the philosophical debate on meaning from 1980, philosopher John Searle (1980) introduced another thought experiment. He imagined being locked alone in a room and having no knowledge of Mandarin Chinese. He describes the situation as follows:

Suppose that I'm locked in a room and given a large batch of Chinese writing. Suppose furthermore . . . that I know no Chinese, either written or spoken . . . Now suppose further that after this first batch of Chinese writing I am given a second batch of Chinese script together with a set of rules for correlating the second batch with the first batch. The rules are in English, and I understand these rules as well as any other native speaker of English. They enable me to correlate one set of formal symbols with another set of formal symbols, and all that "formal" means here is that I can identify the symbols entirely by their shapes . . . For the purposes of the Chinese, I am simply an instantiation of the computer program. (Searle, 1980, pp. 417-418)

This is, in essence, a counterargument to Turing's (1950) position mentioned earlier. Searle posits that it would be absurd to assume that the person in the room, in this case, himself, would speak or understand Chinese under these conditions. Yet, from an external viewpoint, it might seem as though he does. Searle's Chinese room problem can be visually illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Two individuals who speak Chinese provide input and receive output. In the middle is John Searle, who does not speak Chinese but has a rule book for correlating one Chinese symbol with another. He takes input, matches it and produces the corresponding output, which he then sends out of the room. From an external perspective, it might

Figure 2.

Searle's Chinese Room Illustration (Source: Wikimedia Commons)

appear as successful interaction in Chinese. However, this appearance of Chinese language competence is challenged by our conventional understanding of language and communication: we would probably be reluctant to claim that John Searle has a command of Chinese. In the final move, Searle then suggests that he could be replaced by a computer. Computers follow programs and may not "speak" the language, yet they can effectively

interact with it. With the LLMs (e.g., ChatGPT) we are dealing with a similar situation—it is merely a matter of a larger scale and a greater flexibility. These models have the capacity to encompass vast amounts of language data and interact with it in complex and flexible ways. However, essentially, the situation remains similar to Searle's Chinese room scenario.

2. Understanding language: The corpus linguistics approach

Assuming the second theoretical perspective on computer systems, Searle's thought experiment can even be taken to the next level by envisioning the removal of the two individuals who handle the input and output in the Chinese room. A full circle where one computer communicates with another can thus be conceptualised (see Figure 3). This form of communication is entirely viable and frequently occurs in various contexts, such as interactions between banking systems. It can be highly functional and successful. However, it represents a fundamentally different type of interaction compared to understanding language in its true sense, which always includes context—social and cultural. While computers can handle language successfully, they cannot be the source of the meanings of words; the meanings are given by social interactions (cf. Wittgenstein's language games) between people and are shared by a community.

The critical distinction to be highlighted here is between form and meaning. Computers handle and manipulate linguistic forms encoded as 0s and 1s; people communicate meanings. Corpus linguistics and other linguistic methods, including discourse analysis, play a crucial role in making this distinction. Meaning comes from the social use of words in context. Social use in context is only possible when people interact naturally. While they may utilize computational technology, removing humans from the process, as illustrated in Figure 3, also eliminates

Figure 3.

Chinese Room Thought Experiment: An Extreme Case (Source: Compilation Wikimedia Commons and the Author)

meaning. We may ask: what is the purpose of creating texts if there is nobody to read them? This might be a scenario in the near future with AI generated text being available in unprecedented quantities.¹ The secondary effect of this

is a potential collapse of LLMs when trained on AI generated data (Shumailov et al., 2024).

What, then, is the response from corpus linguistics? A human-written definition of corpus linguistics is offered here to counterbalance the ChatGPT-generated definition quoted above. As Brezina and McEnergy (2020, p. 11) state:

Corpus linguistics is an approach to the study of language that uses computers to analyse large amounts of language data, both written and spoken, which we call corpora (sg. corpus). This simple definition situates corpus linguistics in the tradition of linguistically grounded analysis that makes use of the development of computational technology to draw on evidence about language use that would not be accessible otherwise.

From this definition we can see that corpus linguistics embraces computational technology, including the most recent developments in AI, but it is the linguist, i.e., the human analyst, that is at the centre of the process. Corpus linguistics offers linguistically grounded analysis that does not engineer the analyst out of the picture, because corpus linguistics understands that the meaning of words is their use in context and for successful insight into contextual language use humans are essential. Let us illustrate this with some practical examples; three broad approaches to language modelling are currently available (see Figure 4, below).

Figure 4.

Three Approaches to Language Modelling (Source: author)

The first approach exemplified by sentiment analysis has been widely used in the area of marketing and product review. It is a linguistically simple approach of matching dictionary forms of words to real texts. The second approach involves complex computational models and machine learning, particularly LLMs. However, these models are often considered indeterministic black boxes, and this has certain limitations when their scientific/theoretical implications are taken into consideration. For example, it is not possible to replicate the answers based on these models and transparently trace the exact source of the response provided. In contrast, a third approach can be proposed—the corpus linguistic approach or corpus-driven discourse analysis approach. This approach can provide insights from transparent evidence interpreted within its functional context. The key differentiation between the previous two approaches and the third one lies in the terms “transparent evidence” and “functional context.”

An example of how these approaches operate can be drawn from the analysis of a piece of discourse. Imagine a text that includes four instances of the adjective “good”; we want to understand the values it conveys, whether positive or negative. The form matching approach such as sentiment analysis might lead one to assume that the overall sentiment of this discourse is positive, given the frequent use of the word “good.”

In the second approach, when interacting with LLMs using AI technologies such as ChatGPT, two contradictory conclusions might be drawn depending on how the question is framed. For example, when ChatGPT was presented with the following message and asked for interpretation, it first concluded that the overall sentiment is positive. The message reads: “‘This is good,’ said the Mad Hatter.” When requested in a follow-up query to consider an ironic interpretation, the tool was obviously happy to oblige, providing the following interpretation, which contradicts the original one.

Figure 5.

ChatGPT Re-Interpretation

The outcome of the interpretation and re-interpretation (see Figure 5) was thus largely dependent on the phrasing of the query. Based on two interactions with ChatGPT, two very different conclusions could thus be reached. The tool is accommodating and responsive to input, which is a positive aspect. However, it is not deterministic, making it challenging to understand how two distinct results relate to the same reality.

The third approach, advocated here, is the corpus linguistic approach, understood as the computer-aided human analysis of “words in context” or “words in discourse.” In the same example of four uses of the adjective “good,” corpus linguistics enables us to examine the individual contexts in which these occurrences take place, through techniques such as concordancing.

Figure 6.

Corpus Linguistics Insight into Contexts

The devil is always in the detail, or context, as a corpus linguist would say (see Figure 6). Imagine that one concordance line states, ““This is good’, said the Mad Hatter”. Another maintains, “I cannot say that this would be good,” and yet another reads, “Many claim that this is good. I don't agree with them.” Finally, the last concordance line says, “Good? That’s a laugh!” When the broader contexts in which the adjective “good” appears are considered, the overall conclusion is that the text is actually expressing strong negativity and dissatisfaction.

It is clear that only by examining the use of words in their context can the true meanings of those words be understood. Simply matching forms or relying solely on a large language model may not always provide the appropriate answer. In corpus-based discourse analysis, the human analyst, aided by computational technology, is essential for interpreting patterns in examples of

language use, which need to be considered within their full linguistic, social and cultural contexts.

Because large amounts of linguistic evidence need to be analysed, the question ultimately becomes: how can this wealth of data be managed without compromising our key principles of language analysis (McEnergy & Brezina, 2022)? Our core focus should remain on function and meaning and its robust investigation.

Corpus linguistics offers a viable solution for this, which relies on the use of specialized software tools such as #LancsBox X (Brezina & Platt, 2024)—which will be discussed in the next section. Many other tools are on offer—see Brezina and McEnergy (2020) for an overview—that provide users and analysts with direct access to critical contexts. This ability to comprehend important contexts in which words occur is the main approach in corpus linguistics.

Concordance lines, which exemplify this approach (Wulff & Baker, 2021), have been described as the cornerstone of corpus linguistics. They allow us to see *all* examples of a use of a word or a phrase or a grammatical structure, which can be sorted and filtered in various ways, offering insights into the context in which words were used. This method is not new; it dates back to pre-computational times when medieval and later scholars created concordances for the Bible. These were manual concordances, involving the laborious process of reading through every single word of the source text. Today, computational technology allows this process to be carried out on a much larger scale, with millions and billions of words. However, the fundamental principle remains the same: access to data and direct access to the contexts in which the target words or phrases appear.

3. #LancsBox X: A software tool responding to emerging technological challenges

#LancsBox is a tool developed at the ESRC Centre for Corpus Approaches to Social Science (CASS),² Lancaster University; it represents a response to the latest challenges in the field based on a careful theoretical reflection as well as practical needs of the research centre and a wider research community. This tool, which is freely available, is constantly evolving to meet present and future needs, with one or two new versions released each year to address emerging challenges. The development began in 2015 with basic visualization techniques related to collocation. In 2020, several layers of automation were added. In 2023, the tool was redesigned to make it more flexible, user-friendly and capable of processing much larger data sets, including millions and billions of words. After the re-design, versions of #LancsBox are referred to as #LancsBox X because of its support of extensible markup language (XML) for the analysis of rich meta-data.

Some core features of #LancsBox X will be demonstrated below, showcasing the corpus linguistic approach to meaning and context in language analysis described in this paper. The users can follow these examples after downloading the tool for free from <https://lancsbox.lancs.ac.uk>. The tool can be run on a regular laptop or desktop with Windows, Mac OS or Linux.

To demonstrate how #LancsBox X operates, we can look at a simple example of a collocation graph (Brezina et al., 2015) and a dynamic interaction with this graph that #LancsBox X supports in its GraphColl tool. In addition to a collocation table displaying detailed statistics, the collocation graph visualizes important relationships between words in language and discourse. Collocates are displayed around the search term (node) on the fly even in very large corpora such as the Hansard Corpus, available via #LancsBox X, which includes all British parliamentary speeches from 1802 to the present—two billion words in total. The tool swiftly accesses the data, automatically computes the relevant statistics and provides examples of concordance lines and contexts in which the words appear. In functional approach to language (e.g., McEnery & Brezina, 2022), the importance of context is emphasized; in #LancsBox X, hovering over a collocate or a word in a wordlist with the mouse reveals its context. The tool also has powerful visualization capabilities, allowing flexibility and offering an appealing user experience.

Figure 7.
#LancsBox X: User Experience

#LancsBox X is designed for efficiency, recognizing that the more data is involved, the greater the demand for the clarity of the presentation. This is a

core philosophy behind #LancsBox X—clarity and user experience. When starting with #LancsBox X, users can benefit from many corpora provided via #LancsBox X such as the Hansard Corpus (see above) or the British National Corpus 2014 (Brezina et al., 2021; Love et al., 2017) that can be download immediately, along with an example corpus to begin exploration. The tool offers multiple functionalities: searching for a word, phrase, or grammatical structure. Multiple tools can be displayed on the screen, and searched individually or simultaneously (see Figure 7). Outputs include concordance lines, word lists, n-gram lists, keyword lists, visualizations of collocations, and much more. Furthermore, users can load their own data in any language, have it processed and tagged (pos, headword, syntax, semantics), and begin the analysis with their custom data. The latest version also enables web scraping. In this way, data directly from the internet can be collected. In essence, #LancsBox X is a flexible tool that offers a wide array of capabilities to enhance corpus linguistics research.

Linguistically precise searches are a crucial aspect of corpus linguistics, as they provide analysts with access to linguistic evidence. One way to achieve this is through linguistically annotated datasets, allowing us to search for, for instance, combinations of adjectives, nouns, verbs and adverbs. The search functionality of #LancsBox X can be illustrated through the following example. When a term such as "PASSIVE" is entered the tool automatically recognizes it as a specific construction that can be searched in the data. It can handle even complex syntactic patterns with ease—this unique feature is called “smart searches”. Concordance lines can also be further filtered to focus on examples where specific words co-occur.

In #LancsBox X, users can search for words, phrases, and even semantic groups, such as PEOPLE, which will return any words related to people in a broad sense. The tool supports the USAS tagging system. For advanced users, queries can be defined using the Corpus Query Language (CQL), which is fully implemented in the tool. For example, the underlining CQL query behind the smart search “PASSIVE” is:

```
[pos="VB.*"] [pos="R.*"]{0,3} [pos="V.N"]
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This query identifies the verb “to be” in any form followed by up to three optional adverbial elements and the past participle. The users can modify this query to suit their research questions and the nature of the data. For instance, in spoken language, there might be additional intervening elements in the passive construction including hesitation signs “er” or “erm” as in this example from the BNC2014: “it had all been erm developed” (BNC214, Sp1m1f253.xml). This could be reflected in the extended CQL query for passives in spoken data as follows:

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[pos="VB.*"] [word="er|erm"]{0,3} [pos="R.*"]{0,3} [pos="V.N"]
```

#LancsBox X provides access not only to concordance lines but also to the broader context which can be copied and pasted into research reports. Additionally, the text tool enables users to browse and analyze texts from a discourse analysis perspective. This includes examining the beginnings, middles and ends of the text to understand how the discourse evolves throughout the narrative.

As for visualization capabilities, the tool enables users to easily visualize data, such as collocation graphs that show associations connected with a specific word, phrase or grammatical structure. For example, the word “data” was searched as a node alongside “corpus” to identify unique and shared collocates between the two words in the sample corpus. #LancsBox X provides a wealth of statistical and visual details available for further exploration (see Figure 8).

Figure 8.

#LancsBox X: Collocation Table and Graph

#LancsBox X also provides insight into linguistically motivated units, such as lemmas and lexemes, allowing for the examination of combinations of different categories of words with ease. Lists of words, n-grams and keywords can also be examined and identified using the “Words” tool. This feature provides a word list based on a corpus, and any specific word or phrase can be searched. When a word is selected, it becomes highlighted in the graph on the right-hand side. The graph demonstrates the perfect Zipfian distribution of words in the word list, showing the rapidly decreasing frequencies of words in the data.

What makes this tool exceptional is its utilization of linguistic analysis. It allows users to identify units such as lexemes, which represent the combination of a headword, grammatical category and semantic category, all in one. This level of detail can be invaluable, especially for those interested in keywords, often crucial in discourse analysis. With #LancsBox X, keywords can be easily compared in different parts of your corpus against a reference corpus, which can be the whole corpus or any subcorpus.

Lastly, the importance of context, emphasized throughout this paper, deserves further attention. #LancsBox X grants users direct access to the context in which words appear. This feature is essential for meaningful linguistic analysis of corpora or texts. For illustration, let us focus on a corpus scraped from the web based on Wikipedia articles related to language and linguistics. The size of the texts in the corpus is represented by the circles, indicating the number of tokens (see Figure 9).

Figure 9.
#LancsBox X: Text Tool

Specific words or phrases such as "language" can be searched to identify texts where these words appear frequently (represented by red circles). The Text tool allows users to delve directly into the context, view the highlighted instances and fully understand them in their contextual perspective. This allows for in-depth analysis from the viewpoint of discourse analysis and

pragmatics. Additionally, #LancsBox X provides access to metadata, offering external information about the source, and if the data is annotated for speaker characteristics, including their background, gender, age, socioeconomic status and more.

An example of a feature available in an upcoming version of #LancsBox X and aligned with the overall philosophy of computer-aided human interpretation of language is “easy annotations”. This feature allows users to define categories such as “evaluation” and their levels e.g., “negative”, “neutral” and “positive” and apply these to corpus data (see Figure 10). The use of colour highlight visualizes this categorization to facilitate the interpretation of the data.

Figure 10.
#LancsBox X: Easy Annotations Feature

Only some of the key features of #LancsBox X functionality have been outlined here. More detailed information is available via the website³ where a full manual and instructional videos are available.

4. Conclusions

To draw a more general conclusion, the key takeaway message relates to the necessity of distinguishing between data and interpretation. This distinction can be illustrated through the analogy of a night sky filled with countless stars, each shining with varying brightness. These stars represent data points. In this celestial tapestry, shapes and patterns can be discerned, just as people have traditionally done. Interpretations of these constellations may vary across cultures. Some might see a plough, while others envision a wagon. When viewed more broadly, a grand constellation like Ursa Major can be distinguished. These

interpretations are distinct from the raw underlying data, which is, in all these cases, the same set of stars visible by the naked eye.

Nevertheless, it is essential that we have a way of distinguishing between data and interpretation in our (social) scientific endeavours. Without this distinction, the process lacks transparency and validity, much like many overly simplistic initial uses of LLMs and AI. Interpretation remains vital because it considers the broader contexts and the various purposes for which the data can be utilized. Although, computational technology can support this process, it cannot replace the crucial role of the human analyst who provides interpretation, guided by tools such as #LancsBox X and using a variety of statistical models (Brezina, 2018) also supported in #LancsBox X through the inclusion of the statistical package R. Understanding the meaning and purpose of the analysis is thus something that should be reserved for the human analyst.

Notes

1. Some sources estimate that already almost 60% of the text on the internet is AI generated with 90% generated in this way by the end of 2025.
https://www.forbes.com.au/news/innovation/is-ai-quietly-killing-itself-and-the-internet/?utm_source=chatgpt.com
2. <https://cass.lancs.ac.uk>
3. <https://lancsbox.lancs.ac.uk>

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